

My Academic Review

Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof

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ABSTRACT

This academic review is about a question I asked in the quora forum:

“Is the notion of division by zero requiring movement correct? Say, there exists a law/theorem that states “division cannot occur without movement,” e.g. you cannot divide a piece of cake into 2 parts without movement.”

I asked the above question on quora to get my work reviewed since it hasn't been reviewed in any Scientific Journal as at December 2, 2020 yet it has been around since February 2, 2012.

The download link for this work is here: [Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof](#)

The Quora link for the question is given here: <https://qr.ae/pNipvw>

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INTRODUCTION

As mentioned in the abstract section, this academic review is about a question I asked in the quora forum:

“Is the notion of division by zero requiring movement correct? Say, there exists a law/theorem that states “division cannot occur without movement,” e.g. you cannot divide a piece of cake into 2 parts without movement.”

There were only three reviews as at January 25, 2020:

The first reviewer responded on August 6, 2019. He claims to have studied Mathematics & Computer Science in High School.

The second reviewer responded on August 7, 2019. He claims to have a Masters degree in Pure Mathematics & Theoretical Physics.

The last reviewer responded on January 25, 2020. He had not revealed his credentials.

REVIEWS

CHAPTER 1

First reviewer:

Answer: No

Reason:

“Division as an abstract thing, like $\frac{n}{v}$? Definitely did not require any movement, besides the movement of my hand typing it.

So division by zero? Definitely not, and that is ignoring the fact that in most to all cases, you cannot divide by zero.

If you’re speaking physically about division though, you still can’t divide by zero.”

My response to the first reviewer:

I asked him “if division is ‘an abstract thing,’ does it mean that dividing a peace of cake into 2 parts is not mathematical? I never got his response to my question.

My answer was later deleted in quora most probably because I responded to him via a question rather than an answer.

CHAPTER 2

Second Reviewer:

Answer: No

Reason:

“Movement is a concept of Physics. Physics uses Mathematics to model reality. It may even be dependent on Mathematics for physical theories to be scientifically valid.

Division is a concept of Mathematics. Mathematics is **independent** of Physics and, more broadly, reality in general. There are many mathematical structures in which division by zero is perfectly acceptable (although none of them are very well known to lay people). For example you could check out [Wheel Theory](#) where, despite the evocative name, **no** movement is involved.

My answer to the second reviewer:

You have avoided my question entirely. As much as division is abstract, it can be applied to physical quantities. It is in this category of Applied Mathematics that my question lay:

Can I divide a cake into two parts without movement; if not, what impact will it have in Applied Mathematics in as far as solving division by zero is concerned?

Secondly I disagree that "there are many mathematical structures in which division by zero is perfectly acceptable." I will quote this statement from Wikipedia [Division by zero](#) (**Abstract algebra**) because it sums it up quite nicely: "Any number system that forms a commutative ring—for instance, the integers, the real numbers, and the complex numbers—can be extended to a wheel in which division by zero is always possible; however, in such a case, "division" has a slightly different meaning."

In summary, my question lay in Applied Mathematics not Physics i.e.:

Can't I divide a cake (in Applied Mathematics) without movement? If I can't, wouldn't it mean that Applied Mathematics is abstract just like Pure Mathematics?"

His response to my first answer:

“Applied Mathematics is abstract just like Pure Mathematics. Division as it exists in Applied Mathematics does **not** require "movement". Applied Mathematics can be applied, and is applied, in lots of applications in which the notion of movement makes no sense. For example let's apply some mathematics to populations: what is the average size of a family in the USA? We are going to divide by the number of families, but where is the movement? Surely you are not going to chop some people up to get an answer of 2.3...”

My answer to his second response

“Thank you for your sound explanation. I agree that division is abstract in Pure Mathematics but what I do not agree is that you can apply mathematics in an abstract form.

If indeed you apply mathematics in an abstract form then you actually never applied anything instead you imagined you did hence that falls in the category of Pure Mathematics and not Applied Mathematics. In short, if Applied Mathematics is abstract then it automatically becomes a part of Pure Mathematics instead of being a part of Mathematics in general.

In other words, if we are to take your argument seriously then Applied Mathematics doesn't actually exist rather it's another fancy word for Pure Mathematics.

You gave an excellent example of what I mean. You said "let's apply some mathematics to populations: what is the average size of a family in the USA? We are going to divide by the number of families, but where is the movement? Surely you are not going to chop some people up to get an answer of 2.3..."

The best way to answer your question is to break down the families into one family at a time then we can compute the results later.

If there is one family in the USA which constitutes 4 family members, then the average size of a family in the USA is 4.

If there is another family with 3 family members then it will be $\frac{4+3}{2}$. This will give us 3.5 family members.

So your point is, if indeed division requires movement then we have to chop the "0.5 people" because "0.5 people" don't exist.

Your point is valid in Abstract Mathematics but not in Applied Mathematics. What you did was you mixed the two together and assumed you didn't.

In other words, it is perfectly possible to divide a person into two parts, of which in this case he/she will die. It's also perfectly correct to say that as he is being divided into two parts, there will surely be movement.

Therefore to answer your question, if for you to get the actual average population you must apply division via Applied Mathematics then yes, you'll have to chop the population to get the Applied Mathematical result.

But if you wish to get the result without chopping people up, then you MUST use Abstract Mathematics where chopping is imaginary.

Therefore in your case, you mixed Applied Mathematics with Pure Mathematics to avoid the REAL consequences of using pure Applied Mathematics.”

My second answer to his second response

I am about to prove the existence of movement in abstract mathematics as you enquired:

A comma is used in separation of words. I will use the same in separation of numbers where, in this case, separation means to divide.

If I separate a piece of cake into two parts, this is how it should appear in abstract Applied Mathematics:

$$\frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \text{ because } \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = 1$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{3} = \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3} \text{ because } \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) = 1$$

Therefore I propose that $\frac{1}{3}$ is Pure Mathematics because $\left(\frac{1}{3}\right) + 0 + 0 \neq 1$ while $\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}$ is Applied Mathematics because $\left(\frac{1}{3}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) = 1$

This also means that since $\frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}$ then $\frac{1}{2}$ is Pure Mathematics because $\frac{1}{2} + 0 \neq 1$.

Therefore in Applied Mathematics, (not Pure Mathematics) the comma has a meaning which is movement (= separation).

In other words, you cannot divide $\frac{1}{3}$ without the comma (=movement) in Applied Mathematics because it will make no sense e.g. It does not make sense that you divide a piece of cake into three parts and end up with one part $\left(= \frac{1}{3}\right)$ instead of three parts $\left(= \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}\right)$ because you were dividing the cake into three parts, not one part.

So what significance does it have? It may not have any significant importance to all numbers except division by zero. See the video [Mathematics of Division by Zero](#).

Therefore I propose that a comma means movement (= separation) in Applied Mathematics because Applied Mathematics MUST be seen to be applied.

It must be noted however that the use of a comma is not new in mathematics. What's new is its use as a way to differentiate Applied from Pure Mathematics, when Applied Mathematics can be defined as abstract (of which is not my view).

When I say I am separating a piece of cake into two parts, it goes without saying that I am dividing it into two parts.

I hope this satisfies you. Your input matters a lot to me because of your experience in theoretical science but that doesn't mean you cannot be challenged.”

CHAPTER 3

Third reviewer:

Answer: Yes

Reason:

“I think we should be very careful when saying "No" to new discoveries in science. A discovery cannot be wrong if it can be proven by repeated analysis & yielding the same result. For instance, any division will always yield separation hence movement. This is true no matter how many times you test it.

We may disagree on the way someone explains a scientific analysis but let's not kill a discovery based on disagreements on literature alone.

So if I am to base my answers strictly on literature then my answer would be 'No' because scientific results are not necessary in this subject of thought.

But if I am to base my answers on science, then 'Yes' because science is not about what I believe but what I analyze.

I may not understand or comprehend the results but I must accept them as they are, period. For instance, we may not understand what electrons are or their appearance but that doesn't mean they don't exist.”

My response to the Third reviewer

I did not respond in this case because he was in the affirmative.

CONCLUSION

In my view & analysis, the reviewers who responded with a 'No' did not find anything wrong with my work, they were **suspicious** of it instead. This is because their answers are not based on a scientific approach but on bureaucracy of the academic system that asserts that Division by Zero cannot be solved.

Even though bureaucratic academic systems are very powerful, in that, whoever goes against them can easily lose their credentials or job, **suspicion** is not good enough in disapproving my assertions on Division by Zero.

The third reviewer who responded with a 'Yes' did not find anything wrong with my work (just like the first two), he chose to use scientific analysis instead (which is the only way to approve or disapprove scientific work).

I call on other academia to review my work in different platforms but give me and others who support my work the ability to respond to their reviews.

Academic bureaucracy brings order (most of the time) but in this case it's **KILLING** science as we know it. This is because Academic Bureaucracy leads to Academic gods who cannot be questioned. Academic gods lead to Academic beliefs where we believe in scientists rather than in science. It is this Academic beliefs that make science (that can easily be proven right) seem suspicious.

In the same way, academic beliefs make science, that can easily be proven wrong, seem complex and confusing.

I sum up my analysis in these words: Any science that seem complex and confusing, even when explained in simple words (& terms), has an Academic god seated on its throne. This Academic god has devout followers who will find any science that seems contrary to it, **suspicious**. Anyone who goes against this 'Academic god' is either fired from his/her academic position or loses his credentials and in the worst case both. The irony in all this is that most of these 'Academic gods' died a long time ago hence are not really gods but mortal hence susceptible to mistakes and errors.

REFERENCES

- Quora: <https://qr.ae/pNipvw>
- Vixra: [Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof](#)
- Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Division_by_zero